

Mercuration of Diethyl Aryl-Phosphate with Mercuric Acetate

E. EL-SAWI*, H. A. HASSAN and M. EL-DEEK

Chemistry Department, Girls College, Science Section, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

Manuscript received 2 January 1981, accepted 15 July 1981

The purpose of this research project was to study the mercuration of some diethyl-aryl-phosphates with mercuric acetate in order to combine the organo-phosphorus and organo-mercuric compounds in one molecule and to study the effect of the substituent on the stability of the P—O—C (aromatic) bond. It was found that presence of the NO₂

group in the para position to the —O—P(=O)(OEt)_2 group facilitated the cleavage of Ar—O—P. The products were *p*-nitro phenyl acetate and diethyl phosphate mercuri-acetate. Presence of methyl, hydroxyl and methyl carboxylate in para position prevented the cleavage of the P—O—C (aromatic) bond. Replacing the phenyl with a naphthyl ring also prevented the cleavage. Different compounds containing phosphorus and mercury were prepared (Tables 1 and 2).

In a previous work, Awad *et al*¹ reported that mercuration of dialkyl benzylphosphonate with mercuric acetate gives a benzyl acetate and dialkyl phosphonyl mercuric acetate. However, in a later report it was found that mercuration of dialkyl phenylphosphates, in which the good-leaving benzyl group is replaced by the more resistant phenoxy group, gave alkyl acetate 2. The mechanism explaining the formation of the latter compound was proposed².

In the present work attempts were made to mercurate some of substituted diethyl arylphosphonate, in order to combine the organo-phosphorus and organo-mercuric compounds into one molecule and to study the effect of the substituent on the stability of the P—O—C (aromatic) bond. The decomposition of these penta covalent phosphorus compounds was found to depend on the nature of the group attached to the phosphorus atom^{1,2}. However, the reaction of the trivalent phosphorus, in which the phosphorus atom is in a low oxidation state, with mercuric salts of carboxylic acids resulted in the reduction to mercury and acid anhydride and the corresponding penta-valent oxyphosphorus compounds³.

Experimental

Series of organomercury phosphorus compounds were prepared by introducing different substituents to the phenyl group attached to the penta-covalent phosphorus. This was done by selecting an electron-withdrawing group such as the nitro group (Diethyl-*p*-nitrophenyl-phosphate) and an electron-donating group as the methyl group (Diethyl-tolyl-phosphate). These compounds were mercured by mercuric acetate in a hexane medium.

Analysis: Mercury was determined by the reduction of the compounds to free mercury with

ethanolamine followed by oxidation to produce mercuric nitrate and subsequent titration with potassium thiocyanate⁴.

Mercuration of diethyl arylphosphate :

Method A: To a vigorously stirred suspension of (3.18 g, 0.01 mole) mercuric acetate in 20 ml hexane or toluene, diethyl-*p*-nitrophenyl-phosphate (2.75 g, 0.01 mole) in 20 ml dried hexane or toluene was added at room temperature over 2 hrs. The precipitate was removed by filtration. Hexane was distilled from the filtrate when *p*-nitrophenyl-acetate (III) was obtained (95%, m.p. 81-82°). It was confirmed by mixed m.p. with an authentic sample and on hydrolysis with 20% NaOH gave *p*-nitrophenyl. The precipitate was identified as diethylphosphate-mercuri-acetate(IV) crystallised from acetic acid (yield 96%) m.p. decomposed at 270-71°.

	C%	H%	Hg%
Analysis : Calcd. for (C ₈ H ₁₃ O ₆ PHg)	17.45	3.15	48.61
Found :	17.13	2.95	48.08

Method B: To a stirred suspension of mercuric acetate in 20 ml hexane (3.18 g, 0.01 mole) diethyl *p*-nitrophenyl-phosphate (2.75 g, 0.01 mole) in 20 ml hexane was added at room temperature. Acetic acid was added and the mixture became clear. The reaction mixture was heated for 4 hrs at 100°. A white crystalline precipitate separated out during heating, filtered and crystallised from acetic acid (yield 25%) decomposed at 300°.

	(V) C%	H%	Hg%
Analysis : Calcd. for (C ₈ H ₁₁ O ₆ PHg ₂)	11.19	1.71	62.37
Found :	10.3	1.7	61.92

The filtrate was extracted with hexane and treated with sodium bicarbonate to remove acetic acid and then washed several times with water, dried and filtered. The solvent was removed under

* Permanent Address : Chemistry Department, University College for Women, Ain Shams University, Heliopolis, Cairo, Egypt.

reduced pressure to give compound(VI). This compound was then identified to be dimercurated *p*-nitrophenyl-acetate (yield 25%) crystallised from toluene m.p. 178-79°.

(VI)

	C%	H%	N%	Hg%
Analysis : Calcd. for : (C ₁₀ H ₉ NO ₇ Hg ₂)	18.2	1.37	2.13	61.13
Found :	17.49	1.54	1.96	60.90

Mercuration of other diethyl substituted phenyl-phosphate with mercuric acetate : Methods A and B above were generally followed and the results are tabulated in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

The mercuration of diethyl-*p*-nitrophenyl-phosphate may have started first by the formation of

intermediate(II) followed by its decomposition to give compounds(III) and(IV). The presence of the nitro group facilitated the decomposition of intermediate(II) as shown in the following mechanism :

TABLE 1—MERCURATION OF R-O-P(OC₂H₅)₂ BY METHOD A : AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

R	Product	Yield %	Formula	%C		Analysis %H		%Hg	
				Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
	(IXa)* m.p. 138-140° (XV)	57.0	(C ₇ H ₈ O ₄ P) ₂ Hg	29.23	29.6	2.79	2.8	34.91	34.88
	decomposed at 240° (XIa)	65.0	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₈ PHg ₂	16.9	16.4	1.5	1.8	56.73	56.71
	decomposed at 245° (XII)	33.0	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₈ PHg	24.46	24.6	2.24	2.1	40.88	40.86
	m.p. 141-142° (XVI)	64.0	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₁₁ P ₂ Hg	33.4	33.1	3.34	3.1	27.915	27.89
	decomposed at 165-170°	25.0	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₁₁ PHg ₄	17.16	16.9	1.35	1.3	63.76	63.70

* Analysis and ir spectra showed the hydrolysis of OEt to OH.

TABLE 2—MERCURATION OF R-O-P(OC₂H₅)₂ BY METHOD B : IN PRESENCE OF ACETIC ACID AT 100°

R	Product	Yield %	Formula	%C		Analysis %H		%Hg	
				Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
	(X) decomposed at 230° (XV)	96.5	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₁₀ PHg ₂	16.185	16.3	1.556	1.60	62.44	62.22
	decomposed at 240° (XIV)	79.2	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₈ PHg ₂	16.9	16.4	1.5	1.8	56.73	56.69
	decomposed at 330° (XI)	47.0	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₁₀ PHg ₂	21.62	21.80	2.187	2.1	51.62	51.59
	m.p. 139-140° (XVI)	42.0	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₈ PHg	27.8	28.3	2.8	2.5	38.66	38.68
	decomposed at 165-170° (XVII)	40.0	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₁₁ PHg ₄	17.16	16.9	1.35	1.3	63.763	63.72
	decomposed at 350°	30.0	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₁₀ PHg ₄	10.66	10.3	0.8	traces	68.324	68.19

Product(III) gave no depression in melting point when mixed with an authentic sample prepared⁶.

Mercuration of diethyl-*p*-nitrophenyl-phosphate with mercuric acetate in acetic acid, with stirring at 100° gave dimercurated *p*-nitrophenyl-acetate(VI) and a dimercurated phosphorus compound (V).

The following mechanism is proposed for the reaction of diethyl-phosphate-mercuric-acetate with mercuric acetate in acetic acid at 100°.

absence of aromatic protons strongly confirmed the decomposition of diethyl-*p*-nitrophenyl-phosphate by mercuric acetate. The ir spectra of (IV) showed an absorption band at 1194 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to the P-O-C₂H₅ asymmetric stretching frequency and the band at 986 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to the symmetric stretching frequency of the P-O-C₂H₅. The phosphoryl stretching vibration was found at 1300 cm⁻¹. For compound₂(V)

In this mechanism an intramolecular attack of the acetate group occurs on the alkyl moiety to give alkyl acetate and (V). This mechanism is supported by the fact that in the initially formed phosphonium ion the R-OP⁺ bond is easily decomposed⁶.

NMR spectra of compounds (IV) and (V) revealed only signals of aliphatic protons. The

the band at 1194 cm⁻¹ was weakened which revealed the replacement of one ethoxy group and the P=O band was shifted towards a higher frequency at 1330 cm⁻¹.

The mercuration of diethyl *p*-tolyl-phosphate with mercuric acetate (1 : 1) at room temperature gave (II) and ethyl acetate. The initial step of the

reaction involved the coordination of mercuric acetate with the highly negative centre i.e. the phosphoryl oxygen. In this case an intermediate phosphonium ion(VIII) was formed. Such a phosphonium ion readily undergoes an intramolecular nucleophilic attack of the acetate group on the alkoxy group. In this case the reaction would give ethylacetate and not the tolyl acetate and (IX).

Addition of diethyl *p*-tolyl-phosphate to a solution of excess mercuric acetate in acetic acid with stirring at 100° gave (X) and ethyl acetate. The overall course of the reaction is :

It was believed from the analytical data that the solid material had structure (X). The nmr spectrum showed signals for aromatic proton. The ir spectrum showed complete disappearance of P-O-C

(aliphatic) at 986, 1052 cm^{-1} . The P-O-C (aromatic) is at 1190, 1240 cm^{-1} , P=O band is found at 1250 cm^{-1} . A band at 1330 cm^{-1} was clearly found in the spectrum which could be attributed to the P-O-Hg group. Ethyl acetate was identified by b.p., refractive index and ir spectra.

Diethyl-phenyl-*p*-methyl-carboxy phosphate was mercurated by the same mechanism to give (XI) deposited from the solvent after the filtration of (XII) (formed during heating) by the addition of petroleum ether 40-60°.

and,

Diethyl-*p*-hydroxy-phenyl-phosphate was mercurated through the same mechanism and gave (XV). The structure was confirmed by ir spectrum where the absorption bands due to asymmetrical and symmetrical stretching frequency for P-O-C₂H₅ at 1195 and 986 cm⁻¹ disappeared with the formation of a band at 1330 cm⁻¹ due to P-O-Hg.

Mercuration of diethyl-1-naphthyl-phosphate produced (XVI), (XVII).

Compound (XVII) was deposited during the reaction time whereas compound (XVI) was produced after the addition of petroleum ether 40:0°. The structures were verified by analytical data. IR spectrum and nmr spectra showed signals in the aromatic hydrogen region.

The P-O-C (Ar) bond is stable when the aromatic moiety is phenyl or phenyl-containing electron donating group while this bond is unstable when the aromatic moiety is a phenyl-containing electron withdrawing group.

References

1. W. AWAD, M. EL-DEEK and E. EL-SAWI, *Tetrahedron letters*, 1973, **47**, 4663.
2. E. EL-SAWI, Ph.D. Thesis, Ain Shams University, University College for Women, Heliopolis, Cairo, Egypt, 1973.
3. T. MUKAIYAMA, H. NAMBU and I. RUWAJIMA, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 917.
4. W. H. RAUSCHER, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1938, **10**, 331.
5. A. KAUFMANN, *Ber.*, 1910, **42**, 3480.
6. A. E. ARBUSOV, *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, **38**, 687.